

IMPORTANCE OF THE CONSULTATION PROCESS

Keywords

Consultation,
functioning,
legislation

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ABSTRACT

Consultation is the information received for the purpose of getting an opinion about the patient outside the physicians' own fields. In addition to the regulations and directives of the Ministry of Health on the subject, institutions also have their own protocols. Over the years, both changes in the existing hospital functioning and the number and experience of employees can have positive or negative consequences. Hospital administrations also have an important role in this regard. Decisions to be taken on certain issues should be finalized in a problem and solution-oriented manner by coming together with the relevant branch managers. In this way, both physician and patient satisfaction will be ensured. Emergency services are the places where consultation is most needed. In order to accelerate the process of life-threatening hemodynamically unstable patients, consultations must be finalized as soon as possible. Recent legislative changes in this regard aim to speed up the process. Unnecessary attempts to complete non-urgent consultations by clinics in emergency departments is also an important issue in terms of emergency department functioning and patient follow-up. In order to prevent this, non-urgent cases should be terminated in the hospitalized clinics. However, clear results and processes regarding possible delays in post-admission consultations are not specified in the legislation, and these issues are being finalized by hospital administrations. Problems can be solved by making clear decisions on this issue or by making new studies on this issue in the legislation. In this review, the regulations and the functioning of hospitals were evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Legislative principles

Consultation is called scientific and technical assistance or consultation that the physician receives from physicians working in a different field, with the patient at the center.

The consultation procedures of the Ministry of Health's communication on the practice procedures and principles of emergency services in inpatient healthcare facilities published in the Official Gazette dated September 13, 2022 and numbered 31952 have been rearranged ¹

ARTICLE 11-(9) It is essential that the emergency department consultation process is carried out in full cooperation by the attending and consultant physicians. It is ensured that consultation invitations in all areas of emergency services are responded to as soon as possible.

At least one physician may be assigned to provide emergency department consultation services only for the clinical branches that are needed for emergency departments other than on call duty, if possible within the framework of the number of physicians, patient density and similar criteria. For this purpose, a duty list is prepared and notified to those concerned.

(11) Emergency service consultation services outside of working hours are primarily provided by the on-call physician of the relevant branch, if any, in the health facility, otherwise by the on-call physician. Consultation invitation and consultant opinion shall be made in writing. This process shall be done with an electronic signature or password belonging to the relevant physician in a way that cannot be retrieved via SBYS, and written consultations shall have a stamp and signature. In emergency service consultation invitations, it is ensured that the phrase "emergency service" and/or "red area" is used to distinguish them from other consultations. Consultation invitations are carried out in a way that can be recorded and stored by the administration through methods such as pagers and telephone messages, and the duration of procedures such as invitation, arrival/start and finalization, and telephone calls are recorded in accordance with the provisions of the relevant legislation.

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(12) In consultation requests, the medical requirements needed must be clearly explained, the current clinical condition of the patient must be clearly stated by the consultant, and a definite conclusion must be made in the form of follow-up, hospitalization, discharge. Repeated examinations and consecutive treatment recommendations cannot be made in consultations. In such cases, the patient must be hospitalized by that branch.

(13) In order not to delay the patient's hospitalization from the emergency department to the relevant unit and not to keep the patient waiting in the emergency department, the examination, treatment and consultation procedures that are not required in the emergency department treatment process are carried out by the clinic where the patient is hospitalized after the patient is admitted to the relevant unit. If an interventional procedure is prescribed by the relevant branch physician, the patient is hospitalized in that clinic and the interventional procedure is performed by the relevant unit.

(14) The problems experienced and problems identified in the consultation processes are reported to the chief physician by the attending and consultant physicians and the necessary arrangements are made by the Chief Physician.

3.6. 2016, the Ministry of Health sent a letter to all public hospitals on emergency consultation services stating that 'The consultation process must be carried out by the attending (responsible) and consultant physicians with priority and in full cooperation, and at least one physician must be assigned only with consultation services, The health facility management is requested to record the duration of the procedures such as call, arrival start and termination and telephone calls in the consultation processes within the framework of the possibilities within the framework of the possibilities by the health facility management, to notify the health facility management of the disruptions and identified threats in the consultation processes and to pay attention to ensure the necessary corrections.'²

In the inpatient treatment institutions operating regulation (Date: 10.9.1982, No: 8/5319), Article 65 states that "The result of the consultation shall be written in detail on the consultation sheet and signed by the examining physicians."³

In the Medical Deontology Regulation (Decision Number: 4/12578 Date of Adoption: 13.1.1960 Official Gazette: 19.2.1960), it is stated that 'The results of the consultation are determined by a consultation note and this note is signed jointly.'⁴

In case the in-hospital telephone system or the physician's private telephone cannot be reached, the time of calling the consultant physician should be written and recorded in the patient file or hospital computer records that the consultant physician cannot be reached. When a consultation is officially requested from the hospital system, a message is also sent to the relevant consultant physician via the message system.

Hospital records should be checked for the availability of the consultant physician according to the call or result, and there should be a written document. Disruptions in the consultation process available in the hospital should be reported to the hospital administration in writing with minutes or a cover letter and the solution should be followed up.

Institutional guidelines

Inpatient treatment institutions regarding consultation processes and functioning also act according to the consultation directives issued by them, and in these directives' The responsible physician should request consultation with a written form (Consultation Form).

Consultation requests should not be made verbally. In emergencies, verbal consultation can be requested, but then the responsible physician must fill out the consultation form.

Consultation requests are made through the hospital automation system. Consultation requests should not be made verbally. In emergencies, a verbal consultation request can be made, but then the responsible physician must fill out the consultation form on the automation system.

In the consultation form, the responsible physician must clearly, clearly and legibly indicate the unit requesting consultation, patient information, date and time of the request, the reason for the request, the contact information of the responsible physician, and the unit where consultation is requested. Abbreviations other than those accepted and announced by the hospital administration should not be used. The reason for consultation, which is clearly and clearly stated, should include brief information about the patient's disease and information on the subject on which the consultant physician is asked for opinion and advice.

The responsible physician must sign the completed Consultation Form and ensure that it is delivered to the consultant physician.

The responsible physician is obliged to provide all information about the patient to the consultant physician.

The responsible physician must ensure that the consultation is carried out on time and must read the opinions and suggestions written by the consultant physician on the consultation form.

Consultant physicians are responsible for following the requested consultations on the automation system.

Consultant physicians must be in contact with outpatient secretariats via the call system to be informed about consultation requests as soon as possible and complete the consultation as soon as possible.

The consultant physician must respond to all consultation requests from the Department of Emergency Medicine for

emergency consultations requested during working hours and for patients admitted to the emergency department within 30 minutes at the latest, and other consultations before the end of working hours. Responding to consultation requests during working hours should not be shifted to shift hours.

The consultant physician is at least as responsible for the patient as the responsible physician.

The consultant physician should carry out the consultation process in communication with the responsible physician. Communication must be in accordance with the rules of the medical profession.

The consultant physician is responsible for writing his/her opinion on the consultation form. The consultation note should be written in a way that is problem-oriented, clear, clear and includes forward-looking plans. The written notes should be legible and without abbreviations, as they will serve as evidence when necessary.'

When the functioning of the general emergency services in our country is examined, patients are evaluated by the emergency physician or responsible physician after the emergency triage is performed and the consultation process is initiated if necessary after the intervention according to the hemodynamic instability. Consultations are made via the existing hospital switchboard, automation, text messages and mobile phones. For urgently requested consultation, access to the attending physician and / or on-call consultant physician is via mobile phone, if not, access is provided from the hospital switchboard. In the meantime, official consultation requests are made to the hospital automation and these consultations are repeatedly delivered to the consultant physician via the short message system created by IT. The consultant physician follows the consultation request from the automation system.

Consultant physician call time, response time and consultation notes are written on the patient follow-up files that may be available in the emergency department or on the physician page in the automation system. If access could not be provided, notes regarding this are also written by the consultant physician in the file or automation system.

It is the primary responsibility of the attending physician to contact the consultant physician, follow the consultation processes, inform the consultant physician about the patient and finalize the patient. Any situation that may occur in accordance with the principle of 'If it is not written, it has not been done' must be recorded.

Inpatient treatment institutions regarding consultation processes and functioning also act according to the consultation directives issued by them, and in these directives, "The responsible physician should follow the consultation on

time and must read the opinions and suggestions written by the consultant physician on the consultation form.

According to the Code of Professional Ethics for Physicians^{5,6} 'Article 19-In order for the consultation and teamwork process to function regularly and to be realized as a physician's right; -When the opinions and practices of different specialties are needed during patient follow-up, the treating physician should inform the patient and/or his/her relatives. The treating physician of the patient requests the consultation in writing. In the written request, the characteristics of the patient and the reasons for the consultation request are clearly and understandably stated.

-During the consultation process, the consultant physician is as responsible for the patient as the patient's regular physician.

-The physician to whom consultation is requested must comply with the invitation.'

In this context, it is the primary responsibility of the attending physician to contact the consultant physician, follow the consultation processes, inform the consultant physician about the patient and finalize the patient.

CONCLUSION

As a result, the consultation process should be implemented in accordance with the rules and patient rights, quality and satisfaction should be ensured.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

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